

PARACHOR AND RING STRUCTURE. PART V

By W. V. BHAGWAT AND S. O. SHUKLA

Structural parachors for various groups have been calculated. They are as follows :—

C : CCl.C = 71 ; C : CBr.C = 86 ; C : Cl.C = 107.8 ; O : CNO₂.C = 89.6 ; C : CNH₂.C = 59.9 ; C : COH.C = 46. It is again shown from the study of a large number of benzene derivatives that the parachor for benzene ring may be zero.

Sugden ("Parachor and Valency", p. 44) in discussing the application of parachor to structural problems suggests that isomerides have almost identical parachors. The observed results (British Association list, 1932) do not favour this view. Variations up to 5 to 6% have been observed in some cases.

Similar variation is shown even by the isomerides formed by substituting the same group in different positions in the same compounds (British Association list, 1932).

Shortcomings of the simple atomic parachors were realised by Mumford and Phillips (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 155 ; 1929, 2112 ; *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 1818) and Gibling (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 299) suggested that they should be replaced by group parachors. Although his work is incomplete yet by analogy, the above variation in the case of isomerides can be explained on the ground that the group composition is not identical. It is not necessary to attribute values to 'n' or 'i' substitution as it results in forming different groups.

Ortho-, *meta*- and *para*- isomerides offer an interesting case in which not only atomic but group structures are identical and yet the observed parachor values are not identical. It seems therefore that values for *ortho*, *meta* and *para* positions have to be suggested, in case of ring compounds. But the results available are not enough to make any definite suggestion for the values.

In Part IV (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945; 22, 115) it was suggested that the value of benzene ring is either zero or negative. In this paper we have calculated the values for C = CCl.C ; C = CBr.C ; C = Cl.C ; C = CNO₂.C ; C = CNH₂.C ; C = COH.C groups on the lines of Gibling (*loc. cit.*). Care has been taken to subtract one benzene ring from another so that no error is allowed to enter due to doubtful value of parachor for benzene ring. The results are as follows.

Method of calculating Group Values.

Benzene : $P_{\text{obs}} = 206$; E.C. = 0.4. Hence S.V. = 205.6.

Chlorobenzene : $P_{\text{obs}} = 244.4$; E.C. = 0.6. Hence S.V. = 243.8.

Chlorobenzene : $S.V. = C_6H_5Cl = 5C = CHC + C = ClC + P_{\text{ring}}$.

Benzene S.V. = $C_6H_6 = 6C = CHC + P_{\text{ring}}$.

Hence chlorobenzene S.V. = Benzene S.V. = $243.8 - 205.6 = 38.2 = C = ClC - C = CHC$.

Or $C = Cl.C = 38.2 + C = CHC$. But $C = CHC = 34.3$. Hence $C = CCl.C = 38.2 + 34.3 = 72.5$.

TABLE I

Structural parachor of C=CCl.C group.

Difference of compounds.	Difference of groups.	Difference of S.V.	$P_C : C.Cl.C.$
Chlorobenzene—benzene	$C = CCl.C - C = CH.C$	243.8—105.6	72.5
<i>p</i> -Dichlorobenzene—	$2CCl.C - 2C = CH.C$	278.7—205.6	70.85
<i>o</i> -Chlorotoluene—toluene	$C = C.Cl.C - C = CH.C$	280 —245.3	69.0
<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene—toluene	$C = CCl.C - C = CH.C$	282.6—245.3	71.8

Structural *P* for $C = C.Cl.C = 71.$

Average 71.04

TABLE II

Structural parachor of C=CBr.C group.

Difference of compounds.	Difference of groups.	Difference of S.V.	$P_C : C.Br.C.$
Bromobenzene—benzene	$C = C Br.C - C = CH.C$	258.6—205.6	87.3
Bromotoluene—toluene	$C = C Br.C - C = CH.C$	296 —245.3	85
<i>p</i> -Chlorobromobenzene—benzene	$C = C Cl.C + C = CBr.C$ $- 2C = CH.C$	291.6—205.6	85.6

Structural *P* for $C = CBr.C = 86.$

Average 86.0

TABLE III

Structural parachor of C=Cl.C group.

Difference of compounds.	Difference of groups.	Difference of S.V.	$P_C : Cl.C.$
Iodobenzene—benzene	$C = Cl.C - C = CH.C$	280.7—205.6	109.4
Iodotoluene—toluene	$C = Cl.C - C = CH.C$	317.6—245.3	106.6
<i>p</i> -Chloro-iodobenzene—benzene	$C = C.Cl.C + C = Cl.C -$ $2C = CH.C$	315.4—205.6	107.4

Structural *P* for $C = Cl.C = 107.8.$

Average 107.6

TABLE IV

Structural parachor of C=CNO₂.C group.

Difference of compounds.	Difference of groups.	Difference of S.V.	$P_C : C.NO_2.C.$
Nitrobenzene—benzene	$C = C.NO_2.C - C = CH.C$	262.6—205.6	91.3
Nitrotoluene—toluene	$C = C.NO_2.C - C = CH.C$	300.1—245.3	89.1
Dichloronitrobenzene—benzene	$2C = C.Cl.C +$ $C = C.NO_2.C - 3C = CH.C$	324.3—205.6	89.6
Chlorodinitrobenzene—benzene	$2C = C.NO_2.C +$ $C = C.Cl.C - 3C = CH.C$	348.8—205.6	87.5
Bromonitrobenzene—benzene	$C = C.NO_2.C +$ $C = C.Br.C - 2C = CH.C$	312 —205.6	89
Chloronitrobenzene—benzene	$C = C.NO_2.C +$ $C = C.Cl.C - 2C = CH.C$	299.1—205.6	91

Structural *P* for $C = CNO_2.C = 89.6.$

Average = 89.6

TABLE V
Structural parachor of C=COH.C group.

Difference of compounds.	Difference of groups.	Difference of S.V.	$P_{C:COH.C}$
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol—nitrobenzene	C = C.OH.C—(C).CH = (C)	273.25—262.7	44.85
<i>o</i> -Cresol—toluene	C = C.OH.C—(C).CH = (C)	256.88—245.4	45.78
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde—benzaldehyde	C = C.OH.C—(C).CH = (C)	267.34—254.36	47.3
	Structural <i>P</i> for C = C.OH.(C) = 45.97.		Average 45.97

TABLE VI
Structural parachor of C=CNH₂.C group.

Difference of compounds.	Difference of groups.	Difference of S.V.	$P_{C:C.NH_2.C}$
Aniline—benzene	C = C.NH ₂ .C—(C).CH = (C)	233.63—205.78	62.15
<i>o</i> -Toluidine—toluene	C = C.NH ₂ .C—(C).CH = (C)	266.63—245.2	57.73
	Structural <i>P</i> for C = C.NH ₂ .C = 59.94.		Average 59.94

Application.

The above average values of group parachors are substituted in a large number of compounds and their parachors calculated. These structural values are calculated irrespective of the doubtful value for the parachor of the benzene ring. If benzene ring has any value, the calculated value, when subtracted from the observed value of any benzene derivative, will give this value. The percentage error between the calculated value and observed value with $P_{ring} = 0$ falls again within the range of experimental error 0.5% and hence these values again support the view that parachor of benzene ring = 0. The following typical examples will illustrate this.

TABLE VII

Compound.	S.V.	E.C.	$P_{calc.}$	$P_{obs.}$	Mean diff.
2-Methyl-1 : 4-benzoquinone	276.60	0.70	277.30	272.0	-1.80%
Phenol	219.44	0.42	219.86	220.2—224.8	1.10
Cresol	255.05	0.55	255.60	257.5	0.70
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	272.74	0.70	273.44	273.2—274.7	0.10
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	267.04	0.60	267.64	268.0	0.10
Aniline	231.04	0.50	231.54	232.7—235.7	0.90
<i>o</i> -Toluidine	269.04	0.67	270.71	269.3	-0.15
Methyl salicylate	321.48	0.95	322.43	322.1—323.7	-0.14

It will be observed that parachors observed in certain cases show a variation of 4 to 5 units. In such cases the mean value varies by 2 to 2.5 units and hence percentage error is high due to unreliability of the results. Otherwise in the majority of the cases percentage error is much less than ± 0.5 .